

The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Solving the Climate Problem and Preserving the Environment

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1. Introduction to Artificial Intelligence and Climate Change

AI is a technical and economic concept that covers the automation of decision-making processes, thereby shifting various value-related tasks to AI systems [1][2]. This, in turn, leads to the establishment of new and innovative market mechanisms that enable the efficient distribution of services and goods across various sectors and industries. Through the integration of AI, organizations are able to streamline their operations, enhance productivity, and achieve higher levels of efficiency [3]. Furthermore, AI facilitates the realization of improved resource allocation, as well as the optimization of complex algorithms, leading to better informed and accurate decision-making. The utilization of AI technology has the potential to revolutionize numerous domains, empowering businesses and individuals alike with innovative solutions and endless possibilities [4][5][6][7]. By harnessing the power of AI, we can unlock unprecedented levels of progress and embark on a transformative journey towards a future that is increasingly automated and intelligent [8][9]. Today, attention is drawn to the effect of AI on solving various global problems [10]. The problem of solving the global problem of climate change and other environmental problems is one of them [11]. AI can provide organizations, either by the state or by the business community, with significant environmental benefits [12]. The use of AI, in particular in energy and transport, can lead to significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, as well as pollution reductions [13].

In recent years, the world has witnessed dramatic and highly unusual climate phenomena: tides, hurricanes, and tsunamis, which have cost many lives and caused significant damage to infrastructure and development [14]. Developing countries, which contribute the least to the emission of greenhouse gases, are at greatest risk from the impacts of climate change [15]. Climate change threatens global economic growth, productivity, and

the welfare of nations. It is predicted that inaction towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions will result in larger and more frequent incidents than in the past [16]. Avoiding these high costs will require a strong response, coordinated with comprehensive energy transitions to change society [17]. The speed at which we can reduce emissions will be determined by a combination of our investments in reducing emissions and policies that build momentum and bring about significant environmental benefits [18]. AI can provide us with innovative solutions to reduce emissions and improve climate change modeling, thereby supporting more comprehensive policy decisions [19].

2. Applications of AI in Climate Change Mitigation

Artificial intelligence has truly and undeniably made its indelible mark in almost every single facet of the human existence, permeating and infiltrating numerous diverse domains with its absolutely remarkable and awe-inspiring capabilities [20][21]. With its incomparable and unparalleled potential, it has ultimately transformed into an exceedingly potent and influential tool, displaying effortless proficiency and expertise in effortlessly tackling and managing an extensive number of a vast array of highly varied and different tasks, challenges, and endeavors. AI has great potential in addressing environmental problems, including climate change, and has a wide range of applications. Some of them are described further in this paper [22][12][19][23].

Firstly, AI may be applied in the limited area of environmental monitoring. There are several methods to monitor environmental pollution, analyze, predict its further spreading through the atmosphere [24]. It can be done using the analysis of satellite images [25], Landsat and MODIS [26]. One of the most important tasks is to determine the amount of air pollution [27]. There are lots of ways to solve this problem. The most accurate is to collect and analyze "fresh" air samples in the laboratory, though this way appears to be quite slow to prevent and avoid the negative impact of air pollution [28]. These days, there are several cloud services that provide pre-trained ML models for air pollution monitoring. Technologies that are being used to estimate air or water pollution in real time or to predict the probability of its occurring are NLP, ML, LR, Random Forest, Deep Data Mining [29][30][31][32]. Convolutional neural network, normally recognizing photos of objects, is used for recognizing patterns by finding in these photos some phenomena [33]. Maximum likelihood estimation is used to predict pollution dynamics on the deep learning models abilities. Another type of data required to determine the amount of pollution can be obtained as a simulation's results of the CNN neural network [34]. It uses latitude, longitude, pressure, and time for predictions. AI laboratory supported by EuroArgo to increase the AI algorithms in both operational and scientific oceanography. Acquiring new and better bio-physical data streams through a combination of air-sea drones before and after marine heat waves may impact the subalpine oligotrophic ocean [35]. AI can obtain the optimum distribution, exercise in-situ robotics in lieu of moorings in rough regions, maximize the use of scientific staff,

minimize the environmental impact of acquiring the latest float data, reinforce in-situ and satellite data, maximize the economic impact, gain experience of HTA procedures and streamline the processes of float deployments for suicide prevention.

3. Challenges and Ethical Considerations in AI for Environmental Preservation

A number of challenges related to both AI's environmental applications and ethical dimensions must be addressed if it is to fulfill its transformative potential. Within the Developmental Context: The deployment of AI may impact the livability of rural environments or foster the ongoing exodus of farmers [36]. The regulation of green technologies, while essential in a warming world, should take account of the potential risk of further fossil-fuel dependency, environmental unsustainability, or the genesis of new environmental hazards [37][38][39]. Given the strategic importance of the field, it is also necessary to scrutinize the unequal advantages granted by the deep-pocketed Silicon Valley funding models and the continuing hegemony of English-speaking researchers [40].

There are additional complexities if AI applications are used to protect the environment at either the national or international level. The development and use of nationalist AI 'border gadgets' sometimes result in automated state racism, monitoring, detention, and slaughter [41][42][43]. The expansion of algorithm-driven surveillance-based policing within the context of green urbanism requires careful forensic scrutiny [44]. Two key areas have been identified in this domain: first, the ethical implications of using environmental data for AI and the limitations generated by different research traditions; and second, the consequences of AI for nature protection itself. These include questions of instrumentalizing non-human entities, 'technofix thinking', hobbyism-motivated AI applications, or anthropocentrism [12][45][46].

4. Case Studies and Success Stories of AI in Environmental Conservation

While AI and machine learning tools for environmental protection are still actively being developed and improved, some of them have already shown remarkable results in different systems. AI models have opened the era of demand forecasts for the world's rarest natural resources - bumblebee colonies. Having detailed data on the state of the bumblebee population in Texas, researchers can predict the cost of relocating each of its hives within three years with 72% accuracy [47][48][49]. The same AI has also approached stock condition predictions and other environmental problems. AI models have set world records in bee species classification accuracy. For example, the previous champion exceeded humans by 6% of the classification accuracy. Other AI trained models can remotely monitor and quantify the carbon sequestration specificity of the

African savannah; predict climate trends in Africa and seriously outperform state-of-the-art global weather models [50][51][52].

Recently, AI has been particularly successful in measuring and managing environmental pollution. A model called AirSafe, launched by Canadian researchers, captures the complex dynamics of ozone, greenhouse gases, and air pollutants. It can be used to guide government and public decisions in thousands of communities [53][54][55]. Amazing has the potential to save human lives: a 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ reduction in annual PM_{2.5} exposure is associated with a 73% decrease in the probability of a premature and sudden cardiac death. Modeling nitrogen overloads by humans in nature with Earth Systems AI can help reduce the toxic algae blooms that cause neurological diseases in freshwater bodies [56][57][58].

5. Future Prospects and Recommendations for AI Integration in Environmental Sustainability

Artificial intelligence is an area that is attracting particular attention in all areas of life today, including the environment. In recent years, of course, a great deal of progress has been made in the development of AI technologies. In the near future, it is expected that AI will be integrated with many platforms and tools. AI will develop a new infrastructure to advance environmental systems - it will help in interacting with drivers and intelligent transportation systems to reduce vehicle emissions. It will also help in reducing building energy consumption and improving energy demands at city level. AI will provide sound management of various tools and techniques of toxicology and microbiology and climate change. It will also facilitate eutrophication through predictive modeling in the environmental field.

Moreover, AI has the capacity to translate long-term ecological monitoring and conservation efforts, which are often data-intensive, into policy-relevant knowledge by flagging environmental signals and emerging threats. AI could also advocate for ecosystem and planetary health in other, currently unforeseen, ways and broadly distribute the economic, ecological, and environmental benefits of automated technology. Sustainable development has remained incomplete in developing countries, a major reason for which is the higher investment required for environmental conservation infrastructure to improve the quality of life. Some more outputs are expected in using AI to save the ecosystem, which can be analyzed. In addition, the reduction of CO₂ emissions, the conservation of ecosystems, and the reduction of pollution are the major positive outcomes of using AI. The AI in environmental conscious industry volume focuses on finding problems in the ecological industry with larger amounts of data. Temporal information of available water resources can be predicted using long short-term memory (LSTM). In addition to modeling real-time targeting and removal of selected organic compounds from natural organic matter, artificial intelligence techniques are

used to enhance the prototype of the icing system. It is important to note that if a machine learning technique has been trained since 2012, an average of up to 90% of its capacity is restored.

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